

Sizzler: Sequential fuzzing in ladder diagrams for vulnerability detection and discovery in Programmable Logic Controllers

Kai Feng , *Member, IEEE*,
and Angelos K. Marnerides , *Member, IEEE*

Abstract—Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs) constitute the basis of Industrial Control Systems (ICSs) underpinning sectors ranging from nuclear, up to energy and manufacturing. Currently, PLC vulnerability assessment practices employed by ICS operators are limited due to their reliance on empirical observations of visible code crashes prompted by PLC compilers. In parallel, the prevalent PLC firmware dependency on proprietary vendor routines restricts the composition of generic vulnerability detection or discovery schemes for zero-day threat vectors. In this work, we propose *Sizzler: a novel vendor-independent vulnerability discovery framework specific to PLC applications operating with logic realised through ladder diagrams*. Sizzler extends the current state of the art by proposing the optimal synergy of a mutation-based fuzzing strategy using Sequential Generative Adversarial Network (SeqGAN). By virtue of critical vendor restrictions on emulating PLC firmware, we also refine the Quick Emulator (QEMU)’s General Purpose I/O (GPIO) and the Inter-Integrated Circuit (I2C) protocols to evaluate and compare Sizzler across 30 PLC ladder diagram programs compiled from LDmicro and OpenPLC projects over five widely used Micro-Controller Units (MCUs). It is noteworthy that Sizzler has successfully identified vulnerabilities in ladder diagrams within a relatively short time frame based on our proprietary dataset and secured a CVE-ID. Moreover, through a comparison of Sizzler with prevalent fuzzing techniques over the commonly used Magma and LAVA-M datasets we exhibit its wider applicability on embedded systems and identify its limitations.

Index Terms—Industrial Control Systems, Programmable Logic Controllers, Fuzzing, Vulnerability discovery

I. INTRODUCTION

INDUSTRIAL Control Systems (ICS) are the backbone for a variety of mission-critical infrastructures and services spanning across multiple sectors serving modern socio-technical societies (for instance, energy, utilities, and defence). While ICS were traditionally isolated systems, they have become more interconnected with conventional Information Technology (IT) environments using commodity software and hardware, resulting in higher productivity. Nonetheless, this convergence has naturally enlarged the cyber threat spectrum and consequently increased systemic and zero-day vulnerabilities that enable attackers to exploit critical ICS components, such

as Programmable Logic Controllers (PLCs). PLCs are vital to the control, instrumentation, and automation of real-time ICS operations with minimal latency. Evidently, PLCs have been a prime target in recent zero-day exploits leading to receiving considerable attention from the research community [1].

Commonly, PLC firmware underpinning PLC application code is dictated by pre-defined proprietary instruction sets embedded by manufacturers and the greatest majority of PLCs map their application logic to physical ICS processes through ladder diagrams. Existing literature has identified that commercial PLCs lack fundamental security checks during the compilation of ladder diagrams [2]. Thus, PLCs are subject to various vulnerabilities, such as timer condition competition, unreachable code, and hidden jumpers [3].

Due to the proprietary file formats and firmware of PLCs, establishing a generic vulnerability discovery solution based on the internal structure of PLC code is extremely challenging. In contrast to techniques developed for general purpose embedded systems, PLC firmware re-hosting for assessing executed PLC legacy code is hard to achieve. Varying PLC models, even those from the same manufacturer, may require different memory mappings of on-chip peripherals. Hence, a generic hardware abstraction layer for multi-vendor PLC emulation is still an open issue that undoubtedly affects the general study of PLC vulnerabilities and exploits [4].

Fuzzing has emerged as a promising method for the discovery of vulnerabilities in various domains. In contrast to static analysis, fuzzing is a dynamic testing technique that actively injects unexpected and randomized inputs into a software application to assess system behaviour. Fuzzing has been demonstrated to effectively identify runtime vulnerabilities, independent of prior knowledge regarding specific vulnerabilities. However, the direct application of fuzzing to PLC firmware presents notable challenges. PLC firmware exhibits significant vendor-specific customization and is closed-source, complicating the application of fuzzing techniques. Consequently, emulation becomes a valuable strategy for replicating the behavior of PLC firmware within a controlled environment.

In this paper, we address the study of PLC vulnerability detection and discovery by proposing *Sizzler*¹ (Sequential fuZZing in Ladder diagrams). Sizzler is solely concerned with the analysis of executed ladder logic and implements a

Kai Feng and Dr. Marco Cook are with the School of Computing Science, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, Scotland, G12 8RZ (e-mail: k.feng.2@research.gla.ac.uk, marco.cook@glasgow.ac.uk).

Dr. Angelos Marnerides is with the Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering, KIOS Research & Innovation Centre of Excellence, University of Cyprus, Nicosia, Cyprus (e-mail: marnerides.angelos@ucy.ac.cy).

¹Sizzler framework: <https://github.com/7linux-0/Sizzler>

novel mutation strategy enhanced by a Sequential Generative Adversarial Network (SeqGAN) [5] formulation. SeqGAN is utilised to learn the logic of mutation operations within the executed PLC code and further aid the fuzzing process. Thus, the use of SeqGAN increases the number of test-cases that could likely be associated to potential PLC code vulnerabilities and enhances the rate of code path provenance. Sizzler’s performance is assessed using a practical, vendor-independent emulation testbed, constructed with the OpenPLC framework² and LDmicro³. In this environment, converted ladder diagrams are executed as binaries on *de facto* micro-controller units (MCUs), obviating the need for re-hosting PLC firmware. Therefore, this work promotes a realistic approach for accelerating the study of PLC vulnerability discovery with no dependencies on vendor-proprietary PLC code. Moreover, the gains of Sizzler’s mutation strategy are demonstrated beyond PLCs and in the wider embedded systems context through comparison with other fuzzing strategies using the LAVA-M and Magma dataset as the benchmark. In general, our results indicate that Sizzler outperforms the majority of state of the art fuzzing schemes. The contributions of this work can be summarised as follows:

- We introduce a novel mutation strategy for fuzzing, achieved through the adequate utilization of SeqGAN, to generate representative testcases and enhance the rate of code path provenance in PLC applications.
- We develop implementation refinements for the QEMU GPIO and I2C interfaces, as well as the Modbus protocol on the TCP stack, to encapsulate wider emulation of peripherals over different MCUs to emulate PLC firmware behaviour whilst executing ladder logic.
- We provide a public dataset entailing synthetic ladder diagram vulnerabilities to aid and accelerate future research in the context of PLC vulnerability discovery¹.
- We demonstrate that Sizzler can adequately be utilised in the wider context of embedded systems with higher code coverage rates in comparison to the state of the art.
- A vulnerability detected by Sizzler led to the assignment of the CVE identifier, highlighting its prowess in PLC vulnerability discovery.

In the following sections, we outline the paper’s structure. Section II provides an in-depth background on PLC vulnerability detection, firmware emulation, and fuzzing. Section III introduces Sizzler, while Section IV assesses its performance on both PLC programs and public datasets in the context of embedded systems, comparing it with relevant prior work. Section V discusses potential threats associated with Sizzler. The paper also addresses limitations and outlines future directions for vulnerability detection in ICS in Section VI. Finally, we conclude our findings in Section VII.

²OpenPLC: A popular open-source run-time environment used to emulate the functionality of a PLC and can run on commodity hardware platforms, instead of vendor-locked hardware, <https://openplcproject.com>

³LDmicro: a tool that enables the creation, alteration, and simulation of ladder diagrams, in addition to facilitating the compilation of these diagrams into native hexadecimal firmware code. <https://cq.cx/ladder.pl>

TABLE I: Taxonomy of related work. **Key:** ●= Coverage, ◐= Limited Coverage, ○= No Coverage. The methodology employed in the organization of the columns in the analysis pertains to the various techniques related to Sizzler.

Approach	Vulnerability detection			Emulation			Fuzzing		
	PLC target	Binary instrumentation	Symbolic execution	Fuzzing	HIL	Data replaying	Abstraction replacement	Havoc	GAN based
μ SBS [6]	○	●	◐	○	○	○	○	○	○
ICSFuzz [4]	●	○	○	●	○	○	○	○	○
VETPLC [3]	●	●	●	○	○	○	○	○	○
SymPLC [7]	●	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○
P2IM [8]	◐	○	○	●	○	●	○	○	○
DICE [9]	◐	○	○	●	○	●	○	○	○
Fuzzware [10]	●	○	○	●	●	○	○	○	○
HALucinator [11]	◐	○	○	◐	○	●	●	○	○
Avatar ² [12]	◐	●	●	●	●	○	○	○	○
GANFUZZ [13]	●	○	○	●	○	○	○	○	●
RapidFuzz [14]	○	○	○	●	○	○	○	○	●
Fasterfuzzing [15]	○	○	○	●	○	○	○	○	●
MOPT [16]	○	○	○	●	○	○	○	○	●
Havoc ^{AB} [17]	○	○	○	●	○	○	○	●	◐
Sizzler	●	○	◐	●	●	○	○	●	○

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

In this section, we systematically categorize existing state-of-the-art fuzzing approaches to emphasise the novelty of Sizzler. Table I summarises these previous fuzzing studies, separating the core functionality into three categories: *PLC vulnerability detection*, *emulation*, and *fuzzing*.

A. PLC vulnerability detection

Several studies have focused on the analysis of PLC security, with many using fuzzing as a method for vulnerability testing. For instance, μ SBS [6] presents a static binary analysis technique to detect illegal accesses to firmware memory addresses. Moreover, ICSFuzz [4] rapidly identifies vulnerabilities in PLC programs generated using the Codesys development environment. VETPLC [3] verifies real-world PLC programs to detect code safety violations through the use of static and dynamic analysis. SymPLC [7] employs symbolic execution to test both single-task and multi-task PLC programs. These studies emphasize the importance of code-level analysis in uncovering vulnerabilities and demonstrate the effectiveness of fuzzing in achieving this goal. In comparison, Sizzler supports a wider range of architectures through the use of LDmicro and OpenPLC [18] to provide internal feedback from the PLC’s runtime. Additionally, we have designed Sizzler specifically for PLC Ladder Logic Diagram (LD) since is the most widely used PLC programming language [19], while other studies mainly focus on structured text language.

B. Emulation

Emulation and re-hosting techniques are pivotal in identifying and mitigating vulnerabilities within embedded system firmware. Noteworthy frameworks like P2IM [8] and μ Emu [20] leverage this approach to record peripheral inputs without affecting firmware operations. Fuzzware [10] integrates an

instruction set emulator with a fuzzer, supplying inputs for hardware accesses at the Memory-Mapped I/O (MMIO) registers. HALucinator [11] employs abstraction replacement using Avatar² [12] and QEMU [21] to substitute hardware abstraction layer calls with customized implementations. Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) further adds a layer of fidelity validation by simulating real-time interactions between controllers and peripherals. Specifically, HIL creates real-time virtual environment that mimics the actual physical system. When the controller sends signals to peripherals, HIL generates and returns simulated values, replicating what would occur if the controller were interfacing with real devices. Sizzler uniquely utilizes HIL in conjunction with Avatar² [12] to emulate Modbus, an industry-standard network protocol.

C. Fuzzing

Fuzzing stands as a widely employed automated testing methodology utilized for the purpose of vulnerability discovery. Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) represent generative models primarily designed to produce new samples that replicate a learned distribution from a training dataset [22]. Various adaptations of GANs have been implemented in the context of automated testcase generation for fuzzing. For instance, GANFUZZ [13] utilizes GANs to learn protocol grammars for testcase generation, while RapidFuzz [14] leverages WGAN-GP to optimize the seed distribution, thereby enhancing code coverage. Nichols et al. also propose the use of GANs for augmenting the seed pool, introducing a notable mutation strategy [15]. It is worth noting, however, that GANs often face challenges when dealing with sequence data.

The current GAN-based fuzzer concentrates on the generation process. In contrast, Sizzler focuses on the mutation strategy within fuzzing, building upon the foundation of American Fuzzy Lop (AFL) [23]. Specifically, Sizzler employs havoc scheduling, a highly stochastic process, which introduces alterations to the target code through a suite of operators. These operators encompass bit flips, byte flips, arithmetic operations, and value replacements. Test cases are generated by stacking multiple operators, with the number of stacks determined randomly (AFL originally sets the maximum operator stack size to 128). This objective is motivated by the varying efficiencies observed in mutation operations, as exemplified by MOPT [16], which employs particle swarm optimization to enhance fuzzing efficiency. Additionally, *Havoc_{MAB}* [17] adopts algorithmic approaches for operation selection. Sizzler distinguishes itself by uniquely employing SeqGAN to learn the optimal sequence of operators, thus improving the generation of efficient test cases. SeqGAN employs a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network as its generative model (G) and incorporates a discriminative model (D) to differentiate between authentic and generated data.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Sizzler Overview

As illustrated in Figure 1, Sizzler is engineered to generate a diverse set of test-cases aimed at identifying vulnerabilities within PLC application code, executed over emulated MCU

Fig. 1: Sizzler architecture indicating the enhanced mutation-based fuzzing strategy using updated sequences resulted by SeqGAN training.

Fig. 2: Emulation approach for assessing Sizzler fuzzing over converted ladder diagrams.

firmware. This process is further detailed in Figure 2. Sizzler records the input/output of the PLC program, capturing both the ability to execute the target code for each test input and any associated order-related operators. When the input produces deeper code paths or uncover new ones, the relevant combination of operations is recorded as a new dataset. Sizzler employs the effector map to document the position of the related bits in testcases. Subsequently, SeqGAN formulation is trained using the logged inputs and the order of the recorded operations. Our implementation consists of a generator that generates sequences of operations, and a discriminator to distinguish between real and generated data, whereby the SeqGAN model is continuously updated through incremental learning. Subsequent to the training process, sequences of operations are generated to dictate the generation of new testcase inputs of converted PLC application binaries over the emulated MCU firmware.

Given the strict limitations of emulating proprietary PLC firmware, and in order to adequately evaluate Sizzler, we convert LD code into ANSI C code and customise Avatar² and QEMU to emulate PLC functionality. As illustrated in Figure 2, our implementation enables refined GPIO and I2C interfaces, such as I/O modules and communication interfaces, with commonly unsupported peripherals by QEMU. Furthermore, we utilize Avatar² to emulate an HTTP server and provide Modbus/TCP communication. Thus, we provide support for PLC control applications to run on various MCU architectures (such as ARM Cortex-M and AVR ATmega) used during the evaluation phase.

B. Vulnerability Composition

Current PLC LD compilers do not have the capability to detect vulnerabilities or intricate logic errors caused by logic injection as seen in real incidents [24]. We leverage such missing

Fig. 3: Typical ladder diagram vulnerabilities.

capabilities to construct 30 PLC binary applications. Each PLC application is deliberately generated with various types of vulnerabilities present in the LD program. We compose the following vulnerabilities within the LD programs:

- **Race condition competition:** occurs when two processes concurrently request the same resource. In the context of LD programs, two logical operands are executed simultaneously and race against each other, resulting in an unexpected output although the input is the same. As shown in Figure 3(d), the output value of y_{new} is changed from 0 to 1 within two cycles, even though the inputs are fixed.
- **Missing certain coils or outputs:** A rung missing a specific output coil, such as Output Energise (OTE), latches or sets, unlatches, etc., can lead to a dependency issue where other tag(s) are impacted.
- **Infinite loop:** The main PLC application execution process is a continuous cycle. If the LD contains infinite loop, it can consume excessive CPU resources to cause PLC to crash.
- **Hard-coded logical comparator:** embedded into the application, which can consequently be accessed by attackers. Such hard-coded instructions and values can be obtained from the PLC through reverse engineering and then modified to manipulate the operation of the PLC program. As illustrated in Figure 3(c), var can be changed thus the whole application will be affected.
- **Missing jumps and links:** Jumps and links may not be executed following the control flow. An attacker could identify these memory addresses and utilize the spaces to insert malicious code.
- **Hidden jumpers:** can utilize the jump mechanism in PLC to skip some elements, shown as Figure 3(a). If the jumper is coded to bypass a single element within a given rung, it is possible that more than one element or even a whole branch will be abandoned.
- **Object repeat reference:** This can occur when one output may be controlled by different inputs. In LD, some operands, for OTE, timers, and counters, could have different results that depend on the scanning of different rungs with similar logic. From example, the $y1$ output coil in Figure 3(b) is duplicated within the LD, and will be de-energised depending on which rung is executed, resulting in an undesired output.

- **Unused objects:** It is possible that some variables remain unused, especially in large-scale PLC programs, which will not be detected by the compiler. Open and pre-instantiated entry points present a potential vulnerability in the system. This vulnerability arises from the ease with which an attacker can insert malicious code into the system.

The vulnerabilities we implement may cause severe damage to a real ICS setup. For instance, attackers can gain root authority and implant backdoors to monitor and control PLC behaviour. Moreover, gaining access to hard-coded PLC applications can allow attackers to obtain sensitive information, such as temperature and pressure values within a variety of critical industries, resulting in unpredictable consequences [25].

C. Ladder Diagram conversion to ANSI C

We construct our emulation testbed by embedding the vulnerabilities discussed earlier into LD projects. The challenge relates to the conversion of projects into executable binaries in order to emulate their application-level characteristics. We therefore utilise the open-source LDmicro compiler and OpenPLC to transform the projects into C programs that could be compiled and executed as binaries. The compilers for OpenPLC and LDmicro are capable of defining values and addresses used by PLC pins. The OpenPLC can also map the Modbus address space directly to the physical I/O. The process of generating C code comprises three stages:

- 1) Lexical and syntax checks of a LD;
- 2) Compiler generates symbol tables such as globally declared functions, Program Organisation Units (POUs), and identifiers declared for enumerated types;
- 3) Analysis of the executed control flow and data type to annotate the abstract syntax tree and generate C code.

The generated C file outlines the PLC runtime, initiated by establishing an array of communication-related functions in accordance with the memory map. This array encompasses both peripheral and inter-process functions, which are instantiated as threads. The LD is subsequently loaded during runtime where the instructions are then executed. The I/O modules defined in the memory map play a crucial role in receiving both analog and digital signals, and serve as a medium for fuzzing to generate inputs for the PLC program.

D. MCU Emulation

As already mentioned, the QEMU open-source and cross-ISA emulation platform was used to address security testing challenges pertaining to control binaries. QEMU can emulate several CPUs, for example x86, PowerPC, and ARM, through the dynamic binary translation technique. However, QEMU does not support all the peripherals for different types of targets, such as I/O modules, which means our PLC binary files can not be native emulated by QEMU. We substitute low-level I/O interactions with high-level implementations to enable external interaction and emulation of PLC firmware over five different MCUs. We achieve this by customising and mapping crucial board-level communication protocols of QEMU, such as GPIO and I2C, over specific MCU memory address regions.

Fig. 4: High-level description of the processes associated to capturing data mutations within the Sizzler havoc process.

We emulate the GPIO controller to capture varying sensor signals represented within the underlying physical process controlled by the PLC; for instance, switch closures and button presses. GPIO is a type of digital signal pin that is integrated into the circuit and can be set as an input or output. By default, GPIO ports often have no pre-defined task, however the pins can be customized and controlled by software to achieve desired functions. In our work, the PLC’s I/O interfaces receive sensor signals and relay them to the GPIO interface. The GPIO then stores the received data in its memory-mapped space. By means of a specialized function, we retrieve data from the GPIO device file through a read system call and transfer it to the memory space of the control process. This operation is carried out by a thread that is created alongside the control process and employs a write system call to transmit the input data. The sequence of events is repeated at a frequency determined by the QEMU scan cycle length of the control application.

A PLC uses I2C functions to interface with peripheral devices, such as sensors and actuators. We use I2C to connect to the GPIO, emulating PLC board-level communication. The I2C communication protocol requires the SCL (Serial Clock Line) and the SDA (Serial Data Line) wires to communicate between the runtime and the GPIO. The microcontroller acts as the I2C master, managing the signals as well as sending and receiving data over the SDA line.

The emulation of GPIO and I2C is programmed on the interface layer and is based on the same logic where a driver is created for each interface. Since we use firmware based on three different programming boards, different datasheets are required to record all registers for the GPIO and I2C. The different drivers are then mapped into memory areas, which initialise the device and I/O ports and select the register to be written or read according to the offset from the device’s address. For example, to emulation logic of GPIO for ARM STM32F40X, where its memory region is $0x3FF$. We define every register’s status and trace from $0x40020000$ to $0x40022c00$. The trace change of GPIO is stored in log files to identify which register is being accessed, assisting with the monitoring of the emulation process. To successfully configure alternative MCUs, the GPIO drive address in the memory map and the range of addresses of registers need to be adjusted according to the datasheets. The initialisation process for I2C communication on MCUs is similar to GPIO. Notably, the main difference from GPIO is that I2C opens log files and performs a read system call to emulate an SDA line, thus moving input data to its own memory space.

The Modbus protocol is extensively utilized to enable Master/Slave industrial communication between PLCs and other ICS components. In our refined implementation, the remote

Algorithm 1 Sizzler fuzzing

Require: $fuzz_one()$, $fuzz_time_counter$ $t = 0$, $seed$

- 1: Select a seed input
- 2: Initialize a queue of inputs to be processed
- 3: execute mutation strategies on queue
- 4: **if** $save_if_interesting(seed)$ **then**
- 5: **if** $Is_Havoc()$ **then**
- 6: Push the series of strategies into $data_reader()$ when fuzzing is executing $havoc()$
- 7: choose the $matebyte$ in effector map
- 8: **end if**
- 9: **end if**
- 10: **while** $t \% 10 == 0$ **do**
- 11: Initialize the generator and discriminator
- 12: Train the $SeqGAN()$ model
- 13: Update the generator based on reward
- 14: Generate new strategies
- 15: $t++$
- 16: **end while**
- 17: $common_fuzz_stuff()$ Execute new strategies on interesting seed and matebytes

master initiates read and write requests to the OpenPLC slave sending Modbus frames over the network (Modbus/TCP). Emulation of Modbus via the TCP stack is performed using the QEMU emulator that we have refined within this work, while communication is achieved through Avatar² and is tailored for different MCU boards. However, the binary application generated by OpenPLC can only act as a slave. During operation, the runtime leverages the TCP stack to translate messages to Ethernet frames, which are subsequently dispatched via the physical Ethernet port using an Ethernet library, such as `tuxep`.

E. Sizzler Enhanced Fuzzing

Sizzler builds upon the original AFL fuzzing approach, and by contrast, implements a mutation approach that is sensitive on code branches to discover deeper code paths related to a vulnerability. The mutation strategy employed in Sizzler, presented in algorithm 1, uses a customised havoc approach as seen in AFL. We enhance our approach by using SeqGAN to increase the number of useful test cases to be used during the fuzzing process and optimise the havoc stack process. Specifically, the sequence of strategies enable an increased amount of edges and solves the context-insensitive problem. In the first fuzzing cycle, we collect the dataset by recording sequences of operations that find new code paths. The dataset is then forwarded to the SeqGAN model to generate new strategies. Figure 4 illustrates how different operations would match with each other. For example, “*Bitflip* \rightarrow *Havoc* \rightarrow *Insert Dictionary Token* \rightarrow *Interesting values*” represents how to formulate the execution path through different operations.

On the right part of Figure 4, a list of binary patterns illustrates how input values are permuted by different operators. The list of operations that could trigger a new execution path is stored in the query. Meanwhile, the position of related bytes is recorded in the effector map. The effector map serves as a guide for

the havoc process whereas bytes causing different code paths are called matebytes. In general, we observe that in the context of the inherently data-intensive AFL, bytes originating from the same section of the input data frequently induce identical code paths during execution. Thus, in Sizzler, a byte is designated as a matebyte only if its alteration results in an execution path that is distinct from the paths generated by modifying adjacent bytes. Because we observed that bytes originating from the same section tend to lead to the same code paths. During the execution of the havoc process, the matebytes encoded in the effector map are subject to modifications by the operators. In the subsequent cycle, Sizzler employs SeqGAN to simultaneously train both a generative model and a discriminative model. These models utilize the values stored within the effector map to generate new testcases.

The generative model continuously refines its strategies based on the rewards it receives, enabling it to iterate effectively on mutation attempts. Consequently, even if initial mutation attempts are unsuccessful on a new seed, the model remains capable of discovering effective mutations in subsequent iterations. It’s noteworthy that SeqGAN is not limited to a single mutation strategy; rather, it possesses the capability to synthesize a diverse portfolio of strategies. This diversification significantly enhances the likelihood that at least some of these strategies will prove effective when applied to new seeds. A salient attribute of SeqGAN lies in its ability to dynamically adapt and optimize its mutation strategies over time, facilitated by its integrated reward mechanisms. The process of training SeqGAN contains the following steps:

1. Training Data Capture and Pre-processing: The sequence of operators that induce variations in the code path are captured as effective data points for training, recorded as $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n)$. The maximum stack size for mutators in the AFL framework is set at 128, which is the rationale for selecting 128 as our batch size. To standardize the training process, certain efficient sequences of operations are appended with specialized characters. For filling gaps in the sequence, the most frequently occurring operators within the current data are used. Subsequently, Min-Max scaling is employed to normalize these sequences, converting them into standard decimal data with temporal features.

2. Model Construction, Training and Validation: In our architecture, the generator and discriminator are defined with four layers. The generator receives a 100-dimensional noise vector $(y_1, y_2, y_3, \dots, y_n)$, sampled from a Gaussian distribution, as its input. The architecture includes two LSTM layers, each consisting of 128 units, followed by a Dropout layer implemented with a rate of 0.3 to mitigate the risk of overfitting. The generator’s learning rate is meticulously calibrated at 0.001 for optimization purposes. Subsequently, the discriminator is trained on data generated by the Generator. Comprising three layers, the discriminator’s primary objective is to differentiate between real and generated sequences, as demonstrated in equation 1.

$$\min_G \max_D V(D, G) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p_{\text{data}}} [\log D(x)] + \mathbb{E}_{z \sim p_z} [\log(1 - D(G(z)))] \quad (1)$$

The output of the discriminator serves as a reward signal for each generated sequence, and policy gradient methods are deployed to update the generator based on these estimated rewards, as defined in equation 2. Here, $J(\theta_G)$ is the expected reward for the generator, θ_G are the parameters of the generator network, $p(x | \theta_G)$ is the probability of a sequence x given the generator’s parameters, and $R(x)$ is the reward for sequence x . The generative model is then updated based on the reward to improve the quality of the generated data. To monitor the model’s performance, we employ a validation set. Early stopping is triggered if no improvement in the loss metric is observed over a span of 100 epochs.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla_{\theta_G} J(\theta_G) &= \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x|\theta_G)} [\nabla_{\theta_G} \log p(x | \theta_G) R(x)] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{x \sim p(x|\theta_G)} [\nabla_{\theta_G} \log p(x | \theta_G) \sum_{t=1}^T \gamma^{t-1} r_t] \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

As shown in algorithm 1, the AFL is firstly executed to record the different combination of strategies that trigger new code paths in the havoc process. We then utilize the SeqGAN model to capture the logic from different sequences of strategies. Similar series of operations are then generated to mutate the seed set in the subsequent fuzzing cycles. The new test cases are generated to feed into the GPIO’s port to test the security of PLC application binaries. The strategies are recorded throughout 10 cycles. Subsequently, the dataset is then erased and recollected through the mutation steps in order to retrain the model.

IV. EVALUATION

A. Evaluation Methodology

Testbed and Datasets: Our evaluation was conducted over a server equipped with an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 3960X 24-Core Processor with 64GB of RAM and Geforce RTX 3050 graphics card, running Ubuntu 18.04. We constructed 30 vulnerable PLC control binaries generated through the conversion of LDs. Each binary was programmed to perform different control system functions such as time measurement and traffic light control, which are then implemented on five MCUs⁴. The LDs were originally acquired from GitHub and several projects were tasked with utilizing them in real-world production environments⁵. The diagrams underwent secondary development, which involved integrating various vulnerabilities into the binary code, as defined in Section III.

To demonstrate how generalisable Sizzler is to non-ICS specific environments, we also evaluate using the Large Volume Automated Testing (LAVA-M) dataset, which comprises of four GNU coreutils programs (uniq, base64, md5sum, and who) [26]. Moreover, the LAVA-M dataset has been widely used as a benchmark for other fuzzing evaluations [27], [28] to evaluate their performance, enabling us to compare with state-of-the-art approaches. The LAVA technique was employed to create a ground-truth baseline by including a substantial number of realistic bugs within the binary source code. Each bug

⁴In particular the PIC1616F628, PIC1616F88, Atmel AVR ATmega 2560, Atmel AVR ATmega 128, and St ARM STM32F40X MCUs.

⁵<https://github.com/BongPeav/LdMicro>

TABLE II: The result of Unit Test

Peripheral	F103 Arduino			F103 RIOT			SAM3 Arduino			SAN3 RIOT		
	p2im	μ Emu	Sizzler	p2im	μ Emu	Sizzler	p2im	μ Emu	Sizzler	p2im	μ Emu	Sizzler
ADC	✓	✓	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
DAC	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
GPIO	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PWN	✗	✓	✗	N/A	N/A	N/A	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗
I2C	✗	✗	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A	✓	✓	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A
UART	✗	✓	✓	N/A	N/A	N/A	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

The symbol ✓ signifies that the emulator has successfully passed the unit test, while the symbol ✗ indicates that the emulator has failed the unit test. The notation "N/A" is employed to denote scenarios where the combination of the MCU and associated libraries is not adequately supported by real devices.

was assigned a unique identification number displayed upon activation. Additionally, we conducted a comparative analysis of Sizzler’s performance against other prevalent fuzzing tools, utilizing Magma version 1.2 as the testbed [29]. Magma serves as an expansive repository of targets modeled on real-world computing environments. It comprises seven distinct libraries and 16 executable binaries. Contrary to LAVA-M, which relies solely on artificially synthesized bugs and magic byte comparisons, Magma offers a diverse range of vulnerabilities that are categorically aligned with the Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) framework. In total, Magma encompasses 138 identifiable bugs, consisting of 15 integer errors, six of which manifest as divide-by-zero errors, as well as 58 memory overflow issues. The remaining bugs span various types, including use-after-free, double-free, and null-pointer dereference vulnerabilities. We conduct the fuzzing benchmark on two dataset for 24 hours and repeat ten times.

B. Unit Test for Emulation

We conducted the same unit-test experiment as was done in P2IM to ensure a head-to-head comparison, using an identical set of 44 firmware samples. These samples encompass eight MCU peripherals, and two distinct MCU chips: the STM32 F103RB, and the Atmel SAN3X8E. Each unit-test sample embodies a unique yet feasible combination of peripheral configurations. The firmware executes rudimentary operations associated with these peripherals.

A comparative analysis was conducted among Sizzler, P2IM, and μ Emu. P2IM identifies processor-peripheral interfaces and provides applicable input data via these interfaces on behalf of the peripherals. Conversely, μ Emu leverages symbolic execution to discern appropriate values for peripheral access and dynamically responds to read operations initiated by peripherals.

As illustrated in Table II, Sizzler attained a passing rate of 82.3%, markedly surpassing P2IM’s 41.1%. μ Emu recorded the highest efficacy with a passing rate of 88.2%. A significant impediment to the success of unit tests within P2IM is the misclassification of peripheral registers, a consequence of categorizing these registers according to their access patterns. Such misclassifications lead to an inability for P2IM to meet the firmware’s expectations, leading to stalled execution. Sizzler’s suboptimal performance, when compared to μ Emu, can be attributed to its inability to synchronize effectively with the emulator, resulting in firmware halts. Interestingly, both μ Emu and P2IM fail to emulate binary files embedded with LD, and are deficient in detecting infinite loops. Specifically, μ Emu’s detection is hampered when registers within the loop possess concrete values, and is effective only when the processor context

TABLE III: The code coverage result of ladder diagram for different MCUs executing converted PLC applications.

MCU	Program	Vulnerability	Crash	Time(min)	Coverage(%)		
					Function	Basic-block	Edge
PIC1616F828	test-i2c	RC	Y	64	93.8	78.1	69.5
	test-water	UT	Y	49	85.7	77.3	66.7
	test-electric	IL	Y	61	76.3	66.4	51.1
	test-i2c-lcd	MJL	Y	57	88.7	77.4	71.6
	test-leds	IL+UO+MJL	N	41	72.5	60.0	44.1
	test-pwm	UT+CH+ORR	Y	60	94.1	81.4	77.1
PIC1616F888	test-spi	ORR	Y	55	91.6	77.4	64.8
	test-uart	UO	Y	49	93.7	71.1	58.5
	test-timer	RC+UT	Y	43	91.6	67.7	51.7
	test-var-timer	UO+CH	Y	31	91.9	61.1	33.7
	test-coil	RC+IL	Y	52	87.5	78.8	67.4
	test-masterrelay	RC+UO	Y	67	94.5	81.4	71.9
AVR-ATmega-2560	test-switch	MJL	Y	50	96.3	88.9	84.4
	seg-display	CH	Y	53	97.1	88.4	76.5
	asm-demo	IL+UT	Y	41	89.8	73.4	51.1
	test-blink	UO+ORR	Y	50	89.6	64.7	40.1
	test-lift	RC+HJ	Y	67	97.6	88.7	80.7
	test-alarm	UO+IL	Y	66	93.7	81.6	74.4
AVR-ATmega-128	test-traffic	HJ	Y	63	91.8	81.1	76.0
	test-train	RC+IL+HJ	Y	63	99.6	89.6	84.6
	test-polution	UT+IL+ORR	Y	61	99.7	81.1	75.9
	test-counter	RC+MJL+UO	Y	31	97.4	76.7	61.2
	test-pressure	UT+IL+HJ	Y	44	82.4	71.1	61.7
	test-control	CH+RC+HJ	Y	49	88.1	63.5	59.4
ARM-STM32F40X	test-clamb	IL	Y	57	87.1	71.4	66.6
	test-intustion	RC+ORR	Y	51	94.6	89.7	78.5
	test-modbus1	UT+CH	Y	61	81.6	74.4	71.7
	test-modbus2	RC+CH	Y	48	83.1	76.5	64.0
	test-tem	UT+CH+ORR	Y	55	88.0	80.0	74.3
	test-mov	RC+CH+HJ	Y	43	91.8	82.9	74.6

Vulnerability: Race condition competition (RC), Unconditional transfer (UT), Infinite loop (IL), Comparator hardcoded (CH), Missing jumps and links (MJL), Hidden jumpers (HJ), Object repeat reference(ORR), Unused objects (UO)

incorporates one or more symbolic values. Additionally, P2IM is ill-equipped to manage non-generic peripherals such as GPIO.

C. PLC code Vulnerability Discovery

To evaluate how effective Sizzler performs at identifying vulnerabilities in PLC LDs, we utilize the 30 vulnerable binary control applications compiled from LDs. The refined SeqGAN model collects data from the havoc stage in the first cycle and subsequently uses this data to train and generate sequences of operators to guide fuzzing in the following cycle. Each binary is subjected to fuzzing for ten cycles in order to record the entire process. The SeqGAN model is then retrained for the next cycle. Table III presents the results of these experiments, demonstrating the code coverage and the time consumption for ten cycles.

Evidently, Sizzler demonstrates execution times that typically exceed 40 minutes. We can attribute this to the simplicity of the LD logic, as well as the inclusion of hardware abstraction functions for MCUs within the PLC binaries. The control programs which use the Modbus protocol to read/write registers were exclusively developed using real PLC models (Ethernet libraries) to compile a set of applications containing vulnerabilities in order to evaluate the fuzzing capabilities of Sizzler.

Furthermore, Sizzler demonstrates a high function coverage rate with nearly every function in the 30 LD programs and MCU libraries being detected under each of the five MCU architectures. Achieving an average function coverage rate of 88.4% indicates that the majority of binary functionality has been exercised. Moreover, the average basic block and edge coverage rates of 71.29% and 61.4%, respectively, provide

Fig. 5: Fuzzing results for developed PLC binary applications.

further insight into the executed code paths. Sizzler detects crashes in 29 out of the 30 PLC LD programs, with the exception of `test-leds`. Sizzler also did not perform optimal basic block and edge coverage for the PIC1616F628 and PIC1616F88 architectures, which can be attributed to the less sophisticated emulation of PIC that halts if non-emulated peripherals are accessed, significantly restricting firmware execution.

The results presented in Figure 5 indicate that the application of Sizzler to PLC LDs yields a higher number of vulnerabilities than expected. Specifically, the analysis revealed more than 20 vulnerabilities, despite that the 30 programs were initially implemented with only one or two known vulnerabilities. One reason for this is that Sizzler uses public libraries that provide basic functionality for firmware, such as timers and UARTs. These libraries often lack appropriate access controls and fail to properly manage memory, leading to buffer overflow or other vulnerabilities. For example, the MCU library does not properly validate the input size or check for heap overflows when it converts parallel data from a microprocessor into serial data. Sizzler sets the data buffer to a high value, causing the application to crash. From the perspective of an attacker, these types of overflow vulnerabilities can be exploited by allocating a large amount of memory onto the heap and then writing beyond the end of the buffer, hence resulting in the execution of arbitrary code and unauthorized access to the device.

D. PLC Vulnerability and CVE Assessment

In order to assess our findings regarding PLC vulnerabilities discovered by Sizzler, we leverage the OpenPLC project to construct a cost-effective PLC based on both Arduino and STM32 platforms. We conduct this analysis to re-run the detected vulnerabilities and verify Sizzler’s generic practicality. The discovered vulnerabilities are incorporated into proof-of-concept projects over an emulated PLC instantiated through openPLC. We select two exemplar bugs that are the most frequently detected by Sizzler.

Timer integer overflow. Sizzler successfully identified an integer overflow vulnerability that could potentially lead to

Fig. 6: SeqGAN Evaluation in LAVA-M.

an infinite loop in the executed program. The vulnerability is associated with the Ladder Diagram (LD) timer function in the code under analysis. This integer overflow is triggered when Sizzler assigns an abnormally large value to the input parameter. Consequently, the program running within the OpenPLC environment becomes ensnared in an infinite loop.

Cycle integer overflow. The `Ui_Cycle` variable is used to control the behavior of three different output coils based on whether the cycle count is within certain ranges. In each rung, if the cycle count is within the appropriate range, then the corresponding output coil is turned on; otherwise, it is turned off. Sizzler sets `Ui_Cycle` to be incremented to its maximum and it will thus wrap around 0 causing the program in openPLC to continue executing indefinitely.

Vulnerability verified by CVE. Additionally, one vulnerability identified by Sizzler has been officially recognized by the Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) system, under the identifier CVE-2023-43184⁶. This vulnerability pertains to a buffer overflow issue in the OpenPLC runtime. It enables attackers to inject malicious code via the `slave_device` attributes, thereby escalating to higher root privileges and inducing a server crash when the Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) establishes connections with other equipment via the Modbus protocol. An additional vulnerability was detected by Sizzler and has been substantiated in [30], CVE-2018-20818. Specifically, a buffer named in `_memory` is declared in the `glue_generator.cpp` file. This buffer is also invoked in the `modbus.cpp` file and is susceptible to being overwritten beyond its 1024th position, thereby interrupting the loop and causing the runtime to halt.

E. General Vulnerability Detection

SeqGAN assessment: We evaluate the ability of Sizzler to perform vulnerability discovery using the LAVA-M dataset as seen in various studies, by firstly assessing the SeqGAN performance. SeqGAN comprises two phases: Pre-training and Adversarial Training. During the pre-training phase, the model employs the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) approach to train the generator to produce a negative sample. The pre-training phase consists of 120 steps and 120 epochs. The discriminator is then pre-trained for 50 steps, with each step comprising of three epochs. Subsequently, the generator and discriminator are adversarially trained consisting of 180 rounds,

⁶<https://packetstormsecurity.com/files/174582/OpenPLC-Webserver-3-Denial-Of-Service-Buffer-Overflow.html>

Fig. 7: Code coverage performance across all fuzzing approaches in the LAVA-M dataset.

where each round comprises three steps, and each step includes three epochs, in order to obtain accurate data.

Accuracy: The results presented in Figure 6 demonstrate that Sizzler achieved high performance for establishing the path of mutation operators. As depicted in Figure 6(a), high accuracy is achieved when generating data with base64 and uniq, exceeding 90%, and model performance becomes stable after the 250th epoch. Further analysis reveals that the model achieves 80% accuracy on md5sum datasets, which is likely due to the datasets containing a high degree of redundancy, resulting in an imbalanced distribution of the data.

Loss: We observed a consistent decrease in loss after the 250th epoch, which demonstrates the stability of Sizzler. The change in loss for the SeqGAN model during the training phase can be seen in Figure 6(b). Moreover, the generator loss drops rapidly during the first ten epochs and experiences a second drop between the 140th and 150th epochs. Subsequently, both the generator and discriminator losses remain below 0.5, indicating that both are well-trained and capable of establishing sequences of operators for fuzzing. The low loss provided by the generator implies that it is effectively producing sequences that the discriminator assigns a high probability of being real. Conversely, the low loss of the discriminator suggests that it is accurately classifying sequences as real or fake.

Vulnerability discovery comparison: We compare the performance of Sizzler with state-of-art fuzzers, including AFL [23], AFL++ [31], MOPT [16], Angora [27], and NEUZZ [28]. AFL++ is an upgraded version of AFL, which uses intermediate feedback-driven fuzzing and experimental fuzzing strategies to generate testcases. MOPT use the Particle Swarm Optimization algorithm to search the mutation operators and accelerate the speed of generating testcase. Angora uses dynamic taint analysis to track the data flow of inputs through the program and detect bugs in real-time. Angora is therefore able to quickly identify problematic inputs and focus the fuzzing process on those inputs. Conversely, NEUZZ uses a surrogate neural network for branch behavior approximation of a target program and implements the gradient-guided technique to generate test inputs. Here we measure the amount of source code or assembly instructions that are executed, where the higher the code coverage, the greater the likelihood of identifying bugs within the code. The code coverage is collected by using afl-cov [32]. Afl-cov analyzes the coverage of programs by instrumenting the binary and collecting data on which lines of code were executed to

TABLE IV: Bugs found by different fuzzers on LAVA-M dataset.

Fuzzer	Base64	Md5sum	uniq	who
<i>Dataset Baseline</i>	44	57	28	2136
AFL	0	0	2	1
AFL++	3	1	19	772
MOPT	2	3	N/A	N/A
Angora	48	57	26	1531
NEUZZ	46	55	27	1562
Sizzler	44	46	18	981
Sizzler+Angora	48	57	28	1711

generate instrumentation codes and graphic displays to present the code coverage rate information.

The results obtained from the LAVA-M dataset were computed over a 24-hour period based on ten independent iterations of the experiment and are tabulated in Table IV. The results indicate that Sizzler achieves superior performance and discovers a higher number of code bugs that relate to vulnerabilities as compared to AFL, MOPT, and AFL++. However, it was noted that NEUZZ and Angora achieved higher bug identification when using the LAVA-M dataset. As the LAVA bug injection technique only injects a single bug type, for example, an out-of-bounds memory access triggered by a “magic value” comparison, some magic bytes are not copied from the input directly but rather are computed from the input. NEUZZ employs a feed-forward neural network approach to identify potential bytes within the proximity of a designated “magic value”. Conversely, Angora uses a context-sensitive approach, wherein it tracks the input byte offsets that lead to a specific predicate and subsequently modifies these offsets through gradient descent, as opposed to relying solely on the concept of “magic bytes”. Hence, we propose a novel strategy that combines our mutation technique implemented in Sizzler with Angora to facilitate the identification of magic values. The performance of this hybrid approach can be seen in Table IV, which illustrates that the Angora-Sizzler strategy achieves the highest performance among the five fuzzers evaluated where 129 additional bugs were identified in the target program compared to the performance achieved by the NEUZZ fuzzer.

The results presented in Figure 7 provide a comprehensive evaluation of the edge coverage trends for the approaches under investigation over a 24-hour period of execution using various benchmarks. A thorough analysis of the data reveals that the combination of Angora and Sizzler demonstrates a superior

Fig. 8: Execution speed comparison between Sizzler and other fuzzers on the LAVA-M dataset.

Fig. 9: Arithmetic mean of the number of bugs found by each fuzzer across ten 24 campaigns

performance, surpassing both the original Angora and other state-of-the-art fuzzers in the LAVA-M dataset. In addition, the performance of Sizzler improves over time, likely due to the completion of the deterministic process stage and transfer to the havoc stage, which enhances the efficiency of the fuzzer. Furthermore, using SeqGAN to learn the sequence of stacked strategies and generate more efficient testcases also contributes to the improved performance of Sizzler.

Figure 8 demonstrates the computational performance of Sizzler by presenting the average execution speed over a 24-hour period while performing fuzzing over the LAVA-M dataset. Sizzler achieved a fuzzing throughput ranging from 0-3500 executions per second, which represents a significant increase in performance compared to other state-of-the-art fuzzers. Specifically, the range of the average throughput for other fuzzing approaches was observed to be between 0-600 executions per second. One potential reason for the significant increase in computational performance is through the use of emulation techniques, where the binary files are executed on their native architecture rather than the host architecture. In addition, the emulation process also assists in reducing the time spent on initialization and setup tasks between test cases. Furthermore, Sizzler places a greater emphasis on the havoc stage, which results in the generation of a larger number of test cases, thereby contributing to an overall increase in the throughput of the fuzzing process.

The performance of Sizzler on the Magma dataset, shown in Figure 9, is measured through the arithmetic mean of discovered bugs per trial per day. On average, Sizzler identified 39 bugs, while AFL++, Angora, NEUZZ, and MOPT detected 19, 17, 15, and 37 bugs, respectively. Notably, Sizzler and MOPT exhibit comparable performance metrics on the Magma dataset. However, Sizzler outperforms MOPT on libraries such as libxml2, OpenSSL, and Poppler, while MOPT shows superior performance on libpng, libtiff, PHP, and SQLite3.

Though Angora demonstrates high performance on the LAVA-M dataset, it falls short of expectations on the Magma dataset. This discrepancy can be attributed to Angora’s underlying assumption that target functions are continuous, thereby utilizing gradient descent for optimization. In contrast, program inputs are often characterized by byte values that are both bounded and discrete. For instance, the vulnerability PNG001 (CVE-2018-13785) in libpng is a divide-by-zero bug, triggered when the ‘width’ value is set to 0x55555555 and the number of channels is 3. When Angora mutates the value in proximity to 0x55555555, it is likely to calculate an erroneous gradient, thus impeding correct progress. Additionally, owing to the vulnerability of the metric to outlier influence, the capacity for drawing robust conclusions about fuzzer performance is restricted. To address this limitation, we employed a statistical significance test on the collated sample-set pairs, leveraging the Mann-Whitney U-test to ascertain p-values. These p-values function as quantitative indicators for assessing the degree of dissimilarity between pairs of sample sets, as well as for evaluating the statistical significance of these disparities. Figure 10 presents the outcomes of this statistical significance analysis. We selected a threshold of $p < 0.05$ to evaluate the results. The analysis reveals that AFL++, Angora, and NEUZZ exhibit analogous performance against the majority of targets, notwithstanding minor variations in the arithmetic mean of discovered bugs. In contrast, both Sizzler and MOPT manifest a statistically significant enhancement in performance, outperforming all other fuzzers across seven distinct targets.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

Internal Validity. One key factor affecting internal validity pertains to the reliability of our evaluation results, which may potentially be affected by random variation. To address this concern, we adhered to the methodology outlined by Klees et al. [33], aiming to mitigate the influence of randomness during the assessment of fuzzers. Another concern arises during the application of the SeqGAN model for sequence generation, wherein we employ the weighted binary cross-entropy loss function to address the issue of class imbalance. Additionally, we incorporate early stopping mechanisms to monitor the validation loss and mitigate the risk of overfitting.

External Validity. In order to enhance external validity, the primary concerns revolve around the selection of subjects and benchmarks. In response to these potential threats, we have undertaken a deliberate approach. Specifically, we have chosen four well-regarded hybrid fuzzers and two recently published emulators from esteemed software engineering and system security conferences. Furthermore, in our evaluation process,

Fig. 10: Significance of evaluation of fuzzer pairs using p-values from the Mann-Whitney U-Test.

we have incorporated both the Magma dataset and the LAVA-M datasets. These measures have been implemented to bolster the external validity of our study.

Validity Construction. The question of construct validity in this research primarily hinges on the utilization of edge coverage as a surrogate for code coverage. To mitigate this concern, we’ve adhered to a rigorous methodology. Specifically, we’ve employed afl-cov, an integrated tool within the AFL framework, for systematic edge coverage data collection, in line with best practices established in the fuzzing community [27], [28]. Additionally, to provide a comprehensive evaluation of fuzzing effectiveness, we have incorporated the metric of unique crash counts. These methodological choices aim to strengthen the construct validity of our study.

VI. LIMITATIONS & FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Regardless of the promising outcomes proposed through Sizzler, we argue that vulnerability discovery in PLCs, as well as embedded systems more generally, remains a huge challenge. We provide two main limitations of the proposed solution and briefly discuss potential future avenues for research:

- 1) Sizzler is intended for analyzing PLC binary applications. However, such applications are created in diverse formats that are vendor-specific. Moreover, the programming languages for PLCs are tailored to meet specific requests of different vendors. Hence, a dynamic analysis of these binaries is contingent on a case-by-case approach, precluding the possibility of a universal approach. Even OpenPLC project provides access to source code for PLC binary application. The vulnerabilities triggered by Sizzler for PLC can not be triggered in commercial PLC. Additionally, there have been specialized efforts to employ fuzzing techniques targeted at PLC equipment, notable among them being ICSFuzz and VETPLC. It should be noted, however, that these tools are vendor-specific and do not offer a comprehensive benchmark. Consequently, a broader performance comparison of commercial PLC for Sizzler is currently unavailable. Overcoming this limitation through further advancements would broaden the applicability of Sizzler for analyzing PLC binary applications.
- 2) Our approach to firmware emulation is subjected to a significant challenge as vendors often restrict access to technical datasheets required to establish a suitable development environment. In addition, testing embedded firmware in real-time, whether on target devices or through emulation, is a time-consuming process. Furthermore, the AFL testing framework embedded within Sizzler is hindered by substantial tracing overhead, which leads to

a significant performance impact of nearly 1300% for binary-only programs when operating in QEMU mode, as reported in [34]. Future work efforts can be directed towards improving the overhead of fuzzing techniques whilst targeting full-stack testing with high fidelity for PLCs and other embedded systems.

VII. CONCLUSION

PLCs are core building blocks for numerous mission-critical ICS however they are not equipped yet with adequate mechanisms focusing on vulnerability assessment nor discovery. By contrast with wider embedded systems or MCUs, PLCs have not been extensively studied due to the intrinsic restrictions related to emulation of their firmware and proprietary application-level properties. In this paper, we introduce *Sizzler*; a *PLC vulnerability discovery framework underpinned by a novel mutation-based fuzzing strategy instrumented over SeqGAN and PLC firmware emulation setup approach*. Sizzler is the first to achieve the translation of PLC LDs into C code, which execute on representative MCUs such as to emulate as realistically as possible a variety of PLC firmware environments across 30 PLC applications. Moreover, the optimal synergy of a (SeqGAN) formulation with a havoc-based mutation strategy for fuzzing through Sizzler demonstrates high efficiency on detecting new and deeper code paths that relate to an increase of discovering otherwise unseen PLC code vulnerabilities. In parallel, Sizzler is also successfully deployed and assessed within a wider embedded systems dataset associated to non-PLC applications indicating its superiority over commonly used fuzzing schemes.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 programme under grant agreement No 739551 (KIOS CoE), by the Republic of Cyprus through the Deputy Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digital Policy and the EU Horizon Europe COoperative Cyber prOtectiON for modern power grids (COCOON) project, grant agreement No 101120221.

REFERENCES

- [1] S. Kalle, N. Ameen, H. Yoo, and I. Ahmed, “Click on plcs! attacking control logic with decompilation and virtual plc,” in *Binary Analysis Research (BAR) Workshop, Network and Distributed System Security Symposium (NDSS)*, 2019, pp. 1–12.
- [2] R. Sun, A. Mera, L. Lu, and D. Choffnes, “Sok: Attacks on industrial control logic and formal verification-based defenses,” in *2021 IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy (EuroS&P)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 385–402.
- [3] M. Zhang, C.-Y. Chen, B.-C. Kao, Y. Qamsane, Y. Shao, Y. Lin, E. Shi, S. Mohan, K. Barton, J. Moyne *et al.*, “Towards automated safety vetting of plc code in real-world plants,” in *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 522–538.

- [4] D. Tychalas, H. Benkraouda, and M. Maniatakos, “{ICSFuzz}: Manipulating {I/Os} and repurposing binary code to enable instrumented fuzzing in {ICS} control applications,” in *30th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 21)*, 2021, pp. 2847–2862.
- [5] L. Yu, W. Zhang, J. Wang, and Y. Yu, “Seqgan: Sequence generative adversarial nets with policy gradient,” in *Proceedings of the AAAI conference on artificial intelligence*, vol. 31, no. 1, 2017, pp. 4681–4690.
- [6] M. Salehi, D. Hughes, and B. Crispo, “μsbs: Static binary sanitization of bare-metal embedded devices for fault observability,” in *Proceedings of the 23rd International Symposium on Research in Attacks, Intrusions and Defenses (RAID 2020)*. USENIX Association, 2020, pp. 381–395.
- [7] S. Guo, M. Wu, and C. Wang, “Symbolic execution of programmable logic controller code,” in *Proceedings of the 2017 11th Joint Meeting on Foundations of Software Engineering*, 2017, pp. 326–336.
- [8] B. Feng, A. Mera, and L. Lu, “P2im: Scalable and hardware-independent firmware testing via automatic peripheral interface modeling,” in *Proceedings of the 29th USENIX Conference on Security Symposium*, 2020, pp. 1237–1254.
- [9] A. Mera, B. Feng, L. Lu, and E. Kirda, “Dice: Automatic emulation of dma input channels for dynamic firmware analysis,” in *2021 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2021, pp. 1938–1954.
- [10] T. Scharnowski, N. Bars, M. Schloegel, E. Gustafson, M. Muench, G. Vigna, C. Kruegel, T. Holz, and A. Abbasi, “Fuzzware: Using precise {MMIO} modeling for effective firmware fuzzing,” in *31st USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 22)*, 2022, pp. 1239–1256.
- [11] A. A. Clements, E. Gustafson, T. Scharnowski, P. Grosen, D. Fritz, C. Kruegel, G. Vigna, S. Bagchi, and M. Payer, “{HALucinator}: Firmware re-hosting through abstraction layer emulation,” in *29th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 20)*, 2020, pp. 1201–1218.
- [12] M. Muench, D. Nisi, A. Francillon, and D. Balzarotti, “Avatar²: A multi-target orchestration platform,” in *Proc. Workshop Binary Anal. Res. (Colocated NDSS Symp.)*, vol. 18, 2018, pp. 1–11.
- [13] Z. Hu, J. Shi, Y. Huang, J. Xiong, and X. Bu, “Ganfuzz: a gan-based industrial network protocol fuzzing framework,” in *Proceedings of the 15th ACM International Conference on Computing Frontiers*, 2018, pp. 138–145.
- [14] A. Ye, L. Wang, L. Zhao, J. Ke, W. Wang, and Q. Liu, “Rapidfuzz: Accelerating fuzzing via generative adversarial networks,” *Neurocomputing*, vol. 460, pp. 195–204, 2021.
- [15] N. Nichols, M. Raugas, R. Jasper, and N. Hilliard, “Faster fuzzing: Reinitialization with deep neural models,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1711.02807*, 2017.
- [16] C. Lyu, S. Ji, C. Zhang, Y. Li, W.-H. Lee, Y. Song, and R. Beyah, “{MOPT}: Optimized mutation scheduling for fuzzers,” in *28th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 19)*, 2019, pp. 1949–1966.
- [17] M. Wu, L. Jiang, J. Xiang, Y. Huang, H. Cui, L. Zhang, and Y. Zhang, “One fuzzing strategy to rule them all,” in *Proceedings of the International Conference on Software Engineering*, 2022.
- [18] S. Fujita, K. Hata, A. Mochizuki, K. Sawada, S. Shin, and S. Hosokawa, “Openplc based control system testbed for plc whitelisting system,” *Artificial Life and Robotics*, vol. 26, pp. 149–154, 2021.
- [19] N. Govil, A. Agrawal, and N. O. Tippenhauer, “On ladder logic bombs in industrial control systems,” in *Computer Security: ESORICS 2017 International Workshops, CyberICPS 2017 and SECPRE 2017, Oslo, Norway, September 14-15, 2017, Revised Selected Papers 3*. Springer, 2018, pp. 110–126.
- [20] W. Zhou, L. Guan, P. Liu, and Y. Zhang, “Automatic firmware emulation through invalidity-guided knowledge inference,” in *30th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 21)*, 2021, pp. 2007–2024.
- [21] F. Bellard, “Qemu, a fast and portable dynamic translator,” in *USENIX annual technical conference, FREENIX Track*, vol. 41, no. 46. California, USA, 2005, pp. 10–5555.
- [22] A. Creswell, T. White, V. Dumoulin, K. Arulkumaran, B. Sengupta, and A. A. Bharath, “Generative adversarial networks: An overview,” *IEEE signal processing magazine*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 53–65, 2018.
- [23] M. Zalewski, “American fuzzy lop,” 2017, [Online]. Available: <https://lcamtuf.coredump.cx/afll/>.
- [24] J.-w. Myung and S. Hong, “ICS malware Triton attack and countermeasures,” *International Journal of Emerging Multidisciplinary Research (IJEMR)*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 13–17, 2019.
- [25] Z. H. Basnight, “Firmware counterfeiting and modification attacks on programmable logic controllers,” Master’s thesis, Graduate School of Engineering and Management, Air Force Institute of Technology, Ohio, 2013.
- [26] B. Dolan-Gavitt, P. Hulin, E. Kirda, T. Leek, A. Mambretti, W. Robertson, F. Ulrich, and R. Whelan, “Lava: Large-scale automated vulnerability addition,” in *2016 IEEE symposium on security and privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2016, pp. 110–121.
- [27] P. Chen and H. Chen, “Angora: Efficient fuzzing by principled search,” in *2018 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2018, pp. 711–725.
- [28] D. She, K. Pei, D. Epstein, J. Yang, B. Ray, and S. Jana, “Neuzz: Efficient fuzzing with neural program smoothing,” in *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 803–817.
- [29] A. Hazimeh, A. Herrera, and M. Payer, “Magma: A ground-truth fuzzing benchmark,” *Proceedings of the ACM on Measurement and Analysis of Computing Systems*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 1–29, 2020.
- [30] E. G. Chekole, U. Cheramangalath, S. Chattopadhyay, M. Ochoa, and G. Huaquon, “Taming the war in memory: A resilient mitigation strategy against memory safety attacks in cps,” *arXiv preprint arXiv:1809.07477*, 2018.
- [31] A. Fioraldi, D. Maier, H. Eißfeldt, and M. Heuse, “Afl++ combining incremental steps of fuzzing research,” in *Proceedings of the 14th USENIX Conference on Offensive Technologies*, 2020, pp. 10–10.
- [32] Y. Li, S. Ji, Y. Chen, S. Liang, W.-H. Lee, Y. Chen, C. Lyu, C. Wu, R. Beyah, P. Cheng *et al.*, “Unifuzz: A holistic and pragmatic metrics-driven platform for evaluating fuzzers,” in *USENIX Security Symposium*, 2021, pp. 2777–2794.
- [33] G. Klees, A. Ruef, B. Cooper, S. Wei, and M. Hicks, “Evaluating fuzz testing,” in *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM SIGSAC conference on computer and communications security*, 2018, pp. 2123–2138.
- [34] S. Nagy and M. Hicks, “Full-speed fuzzing: Reducing fuzzing overhead through coverage-guided tracing,” in *2019 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. IEEE, 2019, pp. 787–802.

Kai Feng was conferred with a Master of Science degree in Computer Science from Xidian University, China in 2020. Presently, he is engaged in doctoral studies at the University of Glasgow, within the Department of Computing Science. This pursuit is generously supported by the School of Computing Science Scholarship. His research endeavors are primarily directed towards the identification of zero-day vulnerabilities in Industrial Control Systems (ICS) and Internet of Things (IoT) environments, with a particular focus on dynamic and static binary analysis.

Marco M. Cook received his Ph.D in Computing Science from the University of Glasgow in 2023, funded through an EPSRC iCASE award in partnership with the UK Defence Science and Technology Laboratory (Dstl). Currently, he is a Research Associate in the School of Computing Science at the University of Glasgow. His research focuses on cyber-security for industrial control systems (ICS), specifically the fields of anomaly detection and digital forensics. He is a member of the IEEE and the ACM.

Angelos K. Marnerides is a Professor (Asst.) of Cyber Physical Systems Security at the University of Cyprus, in the Department of Electrical & Computer Engineering and KIOS Research and Innovation Centre of Excellence. Previously, he was a Professor (Assoc.) at the University of Glasgow, leading the Glasgow Cyber Defence Group. His research has received significant funding by both industry and governmental bodies, focuses on security and resilience in Cyber Physical Systems and programmable networks.

A member of IEEE and ACM since 2007, he has played significant roles in various IEEE conferences, earning IEEE CoMSoc contribution awards in 2016 and 2018. He completed his PhD in Computer Science from Lancaster University in 2011, and has held lectureships and postdoctoral positions at institutions including Carnegie Mellon University, University of Porto, University College London, and Lancaster University.